

LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT OF HIGH PERFORMANCE NANOCELLULOSE-REINFORCED ADVANCED FIBRE COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The research and development of nanocellulose-reinforced polymer composites have dramatically increased in the recent years due to the possibility of exploiting the high tensile stiffness and strength of nanocellulose. In the work, the environmental impacts of bacterial cellulose (BC)- and nanofibrillated cellulose (NFC)-reinforced epoxy composites were evaluated using life cycle assessment (LCA). Neat polylactide (PLA) and 30% randomly oriented glass fibre-reinforced polypropylene (GF/PP) composites were used as benchmark materials for comparison. Our cradle-to-gate LCA showed that BC- and NFC-reinforced epoxy composites have higher global warming potential (GWP) and abiotic depletion potential of fossil fuels (ADf) compared to neat PLA and GF/PP even though the specific tensile moduli of the nanocellulose-reinforced epoxy composites are higher than neat PLA and GF/PP. However, when the use phase and the end-of-life of nanocellulose-reinforced epoxy composites were considered, the “green credentials” of nanocellulose-reinforced epoxy composites are comparable to that of neat PLA and GF/PP composites. Our life cycle scenario analysis showed that the cradle-to-grave GWP and ADf of BC- and NFC-reinforced epoxy composites could be lower than neat PLA when the composites contains more than 60 vol.-% nanocellulose. Our LCA model suggests that nanocellulose-reinforced epoxy composites with high nanocellulose loading is desired to produce materials with “greener credentials” than the best performing commercially available bio-derived polymer.

1 INTRODUCTION

Nanocellulose can be produced via two approaches: top-down and bottom-up. In the top-down approach, (ligno)cellulosic biomass, such as wood fibres, is disintegrated into nanofibres. The earliest report on the preparation of wood-derived nanocellulose from (ligno)cellulosic biomass was presented by Wurhmann et al. [1]. The authors disintegrated ramie, hemp and cotton fibres using high intensity ultrasound into their respective elementary fibrils with diameters as small as 6 nm. Later, Herrick et al. [2] and Turbak et al. [3] used high pressure homogenisers to reduce the diameter of wood pulp to 10 nm. Wood-derived nanocellulose can also be produced using stone grinders [4], whereby the high shearing forces generated by the static and rotating grinding stones fibrillates micrometre-sized pulp

fibres into cellulose nanofibres. The bottom-up approach, on the other hand, utilises the fermentation of low molecular weight sugars using cellulose-producing bacteria, such as from the *Acetobacter* species, to synthesise nanocellulose [5]. Nanocellulose synthesised by bacteria, herein termed bacterial cellulose (BC), is pure cellulose without impurities that are typically present in wood-derived nanocellulose, herein termed nanofibrillated cellulose (NFC), such as hemicellulose, pectin and traces of lignin. In addition to this, both BC and NFC possess cellulose-I structure [6]. Even though BC possesses higher degree of crystallinity compared to NFC (72% for BC and 41% for NFC, respectively, based on area under the X-ray diffraction spectra), both BC and NFC were found to possess similar reinforcing ability for polymers [7].

The first use of nanocellulose as reinforcement in polymers, namely polypropylene, polystyrene and polyethylene, was reported by Boldizar et al. [8]. The authors found that the tensile modulus increased from 2.4 GPa for neat polystyrene to 5.2 GPa for polystyrene reinforced with 40 wt.-% NFC. Yano et al. [9] reported tensile modulus and strength of up to 20 GPa and 325 MPa, respectively, for BC-reinforced epoxy composites containing 65 wt.-% BC loading. Tensile modulus and strength of up to 8 GPa and 202 MPa, respectively, have also been obtained for NFC-reinforced hydroxyethyl cellulose composites containing 68 wt.-% NFC loading [10]. It is therefore evident that high performance BC- and NFC-reinforced polymer composites can be produced. However, one major question still remains: “Are nanocellulose-reinforced polymer composites truly environmentally friendly compared to commercially available renewable polymers and engineering materials?” Li et al. [11] recently used life cycle assessment (LCA) to analyse the environmental impact associated with the production of NFC using high pressure homogenisation and high intensity sonication. TEMPO-oxidised and chloroacetic acid-etherified kraft pulp were chosen as the starting materials in their LCA model as the negative charge introduced by TEMPO oxidation and chloroacetic acid etherification is anticipated to ease the disruption of the hydrogen bonds between adjacent cellulose molecules, facilitating the fibrillation of kraft pulp to NFC [12]. It should be noted that in their LCA model [11], the authors assumed that the quality of the NFC is independent of starting material and production route. The authors found that NFC produced from high-pressure homogenisation of TEMPO-oxidised kraft pulp has the lowest environmental impact among all the NFC production routes studied. In a recent LCA study conducted by Hohenthal et al. [13], the non-renewable energy consumption associated with the production of NFC nanopaper was estimated to be 107.5 MJ kg⁻¹. This is significantly higher than the energy consumed for the production of polylactide (PLA), which is estimated to consume only 42 MJ kg⁻¹ [14] of energy.

With increasing demand for environmental friendlier materials, it is timely to investigate the environmental impact associated with the manufacturing of nanocellulose-reinforced polymer composites. Therefore in this work, we quantify the environmental impacts associated with the manufacturing of BC- and NFC-reinforced polymer composites through a life cycle assessment approach, starting from the production of nanocellulose (i.e. the cradle) to end product (i.e. the gate) of the nanocellulose-reinforced polymer composites.

2 METHODOLOGY

LCA is the internationally recognised method used to assess of the environmental performance of a product. ISO 14040:2006 (E) states that LCA should “consider the entire life cycle of a product from raw material extraction and acquisition, through energy and material production and manufacturing, to use and end-of-life treatment and final disposal”. Any LCA study should start with a carefully defined scope of the study, functional unit and system boundaries. These elements are the guideline that will help reaching a conclusion that answers the initial objective of the LCA; whether it is the comparison of different products or the identification of a “hotspot”. Following this step, a life cycle inventory (LCI) consisting of the materials and energy used in every step of the life cycle is compiled. Using this LCI, life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) can then be conducted. All the inputs and outputs of the system are allocated to the different environmental impact categories. Finally, the outcome of the LCA

can be given in the form of interpretations and recommendations to lower the environmental burden of the system [15].

2.1 Goal and scope definition

The aim of this study is to evaluate the environmental impacts of high performance BC- and NFC-reinforced epoxy composites through a cradle-to-grave LCA including their manufacturing, use phase and end-of-life. Two commercially available benchmark materials were chosen for comparison: (i) 30 wt.-% randomly oriented glass fibre-reinforced polypropylene (GF/PP) composites and (ii) polylactide, which is considered the best performing bio-derived polymer [3]. The system boundary for our nanocellulose-reinforced epoxy composites and our benchmark materials is shown schematically in Figure 1. A distinction is made between the foreground system, which is defined as the processes of main importance in regards to the study (direct measurements can often be taken), and the background system, which is defined as the processes used to support the foreground system (supply of energy and materials) [16].

Figure 1: Schematic diagram showing the system boundaries of the model representing the life cycle of BC- and NFC-reinforced polymer composites (left), and PLA and GF/PP composite (right). The red, blue and green arrows represent consumables or raw materials required, energy input and waste (materials and energy), respectively.

2.2 Functional unit

A functional unit (f.u.) quantifies the function provided by the analysed system and provides a base for comparison with alternative systems. In order to compare our four different materials with different mechanical performances, a performance indicator found using Ashby's method [17] based on the specific tensile stiffness of the materials is used to calculate the equivalent mass of the material required to reach the same level of performance. The equivalent mass of material required is expressed as:

$$\frac{m - m_{ref}}{m_{ref}} = \frac{E_{ref} / \rho_{ref}}{E / \rho} - 1 \quad (1)$$

where m , E , ρ are the mass, tensile modulus and density of BC-reinforced epoxy composites, GF/PP model composites and neat PLA, respectively. m_{ref} , E_{ref} and ρ_{ref} are the mass, tensile stiffness and density of a reference material. In our LCA model, $m_{ref} = 1$ kg of NFC-reinforced epoxy

composite is arbitrarily chosen as our reference. The mass of materials compared in this LCA model along with materials properties are summarised in Table 1.

Material	E (GPa)	ρ (kg m ⁻³)	E/ ρ (GPa m ³ kg ⁻¹)	m (total) (kg)	m (reinforcement) (kg)
PLA	3.9 ± 0.2	1210	3.22	1.96	0
GF/PP	5.7	1120	5.09	1.24	0.392
NFC/epoxy	8.5 ± 0.2	1350	6.30	1.00	0.650
BC/epoxy	7.1 ± 0.1	1320	5.38	1.17	0.653

Table 1: The functional unit used in this LCA study. E, ρ and m denote the tensile modulus, density and equivalent mass of the materials required.

2.3 Calculation method and impact categories

Our LCA model uses the CML 2001 impact assessment method (April 2013 version) developed by the Centre for Environmental Science in Leiden University [18] using a life cycle engineering software, GaBi (version 6, PE International, Leinfelden-Echterdingen, Germany). This method uses midpoint indicators to model at an early stage the effects of substances on the environment at an early stage (also known as problem-oriented approach), which minimises uncertainties [19]. The chosen impact indicators for this LCA study along with their brief description are summarised in table 2. These impact categories have been chosen based on their significance to this LCA model and their link to distinct environmental mechanisms.

Impact indicators (Unit)	Description
GWP (Global warming potential in CO ₂ eq)	This takes into accounts the emissions of gas that will contribute to the greenhouse effects (heating effect due to the exposition of gases to sunrays) such as CO ₂ , CH ₄ , N ₂ O and CFCs.
AP (Acidification potential in SO ₂ eq)	The emissions of SO ₂ , NO _x and NH ₃ are responsible for the general acidification of soils and waters that ultimately leads to less available nutrients for plants.
ADf (Abiotic depletion potential - fossil fuel in MJ)	This impact only accounts for the energy consumption linked to non-renewable fossil resources. It is only a part of the CED (cumulative energy demand)
POCP (Photochemical ozone creation potential in ethene eq)	Related to the catalyst effect of the VOC to form NO ₂ . Ozone creation has a negative impact on both human health and ecosystems.
FETP (Freshwater ecotoxicity potential in DCB eq)	Measured in Dichlorobenzene equivalent. Important in systems using large amounts of water that can become contaminated by chemicals.

Table 2: The impact categories used in this LCA study and their brief description.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A cradle-to-gate LCA model includes all steps from raw materials extraction to the finished product at the factory gate. The cradle-to-gate GWP and ADf associated with the production of PLA, GF/PP, BC- and NFC-reinforced epoxy composites are shown in figure 2. Even though the equivalent mass of neat PLA is larger, the GWP of neat PLA is lower than GF/PP. This could be attributed to the 1.9 kg CO₂ eq kg⁻¹ of environmental credits of PLA as a result of carbon sequestration associated with corn production [14], whereby for 1 kg of PLA, 2.5 kg of corn is needed. The ADf for PLA however, is higher than that of GF/PP. As GF/PP possess higher tensile modulus compared to PLA (5.7 GPa vs 3.9 GPa), the equivalent mass of GF/PP required would be much smaller than that of PLA to sustain the same tensile load, leading to the observed lower environmental impact of GF/PP in other impact

categories. Nevertheless, both BC- and NFC-reinforced epoxy composites have higher environmental impacts compared to our benchmark PLA and GF/PP. The results showed that the GWP of both BC- and NFC-reinforced epoxy composites are higher than that of PLA and GF/PP. Furthermore, the ADF of the production of BC-reinforced epoxy composites was found to be 2.4 and 2.6 times higher than neat PLA and GF/PP (see Figure 2), respectively, even though BC-reinforced epoxy composites possess higher tensile modulus compared to neat PLA and GF/PP, implying that we need less BC-reinforced epoxy composites to comply with the functional unit. Similar observations could also be made for NFC-reinforced epoxy composite, whereby higher ADF is observed for the manufacturing these composites compared to neat PLA and GF/PP. The higher GWP and ADF associated with the manufacturing of BC- and NFC-reinforced epoxy composites suggest that nanocellulose-reinforced polymer composites might not be environmental friendlier than commercially available bio-derived polymer, such as PLA or engineering materials, such as GF/PP composites.

Figure 2: Global warming potential and fossil energy consumption for the production (from cradle-to-gate) of our two benchmark materials and two nanocellulose-reinforced composites.

From Figure 2, it can be seen that one of the major contributors to the environment is the

manufacturing of BC- and NFC-reinforced epoxy composites based on the VARI. This is due to the consumables used in the manufacturing processes, many of which are not eco-friendly. Table 3 further shows the contributions of the consumables used in the VARI process to the environment. These consumables constitute to approximately 24% and 45% of the total ADF associated with the VARI process of BC- and NFC-reinforced epoxy composites, respectively. The production of the porous flow medium used in the VARI, for example, has almost as high ADF as the production of the epoxy resin used. Furthermore, it can also be seen from figure 2 that the GWP and ADF for the production of BC- and NFC-reinforced epoxy composites stems from the production of the reinforcing phase, i.e. the production NFC from wood pulp and the biosynthesis of BC from low molecular weight sugar. It should also be noted that the equivalent mass of glass fibres, NFC and BC considered in this study are different (see table 1). Therefore, the higher GWP and ADF for the production of NFC can be attributed to the larger amount of NFC required to reinforce the epoxy matrix (versus the amount of GF required in the PP). Nonetheless, it is clear that the production process of BC is much more energy intensive, leading to higher ADF compared to the production of NFC and GF, even when the differences in the mass of NFC and GF are considered. This is due to the energy required to produce the chemicals used for the HS medium.

Consumables used	GWP (kg CO ₂ eq/f.u.)	ADf (MJ/f.u.)
Resin feed tube	0.07	1.96
Porous medium	1.30	33.66
Sealants	0.41	11.38
Vacuum bag	0.55	6.29
Consumables end-of-life	0.30	-4.48

Table 3: Detailed impacts associated with the production of the BC- and NFC-reinforced epoxy composites.

Figure 3: Detailed hot spot analysis of the production of bacterial cellulose

To further elucidate this, a detailed hot spot analysis of the relative environmental impacts associated with the synthesis of BC is shown figure 3. The production of the glucose used for the HS medium (4.08 kg per functional unit) contributes 61 MJ in the ADF category. This accounts for half of the ADF in the production of 0.653 kg of BC (131 MJ) and accounts for 25% of the ADF in production of 1.17 kg of BC-reinforced epoxy composites (272 MJ). Nevertheless, the production of glucose also provides an environmental credit in the GWP indicator as glucose is produced from starch, which is in

turn obtained from corn cultivation where carbon dioxide can be sequestered. In addition to this, the use of disodium phosphate in HS medium is also a major contributor to the acidification potential and freshwater ecotoxicity potential of the BC-reinforced epoxy composite accounting for respectively 21% and 37% of these impacts. The environmental burden associated with BC production also originates from the purification of BC after culturing in HS medium. The cultured BC pellicles have to be washed and purified to remove any chemicals and bacteria used in HS medium as highly purified BC pellicles possess better thermal stability, thermo-mechanical and mechanical properties. Our LCA model results show that this purification step, equivalent to 2.6 kg CO₂ eq, contributes 54% and 19% of the GWP of the BC production (see Figure 3) and the BC-reinforced epoxy composite manufacturing respectively. In terms of ADF, the 22.7 MJ required for the purification corresponds to 17% of the BC production.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this work, a cradle-to-gate LCA of BC- and NFC-reinforced epoxy composites was performed to evaluate their environmental impacts starting from the production of NFC or BC to the end-of-life of the nanocellulose-reinforced epoxy composites. Neat PLA and 30% randomly oriented GF/PP were used as benchmark materials for comparison. To compare the environmental performance of materials with different mechanical performance, specific tensile moduli of the materials were used to evaluate the equivalent mass of the material required to achieve the same uniaxial tensile load. For the manufacturing phase, our study showed that amongst the four materials compared, BC- and NFC-reinforced epoxy composites have higher GWP (13.8 kg CO₂ eq for BC-reinforced epoxy and 8.6 kg CO₂ eq for NFC-reinforced epoxy) and ADF (271.6 MJ for BC-reinforced epoxy and 149.6 MJ for NFC-reinforced epoxy) compared to neat PLA and GF/PP even though the specific tensile moduli of the nanocellulose-reinforced epoxy composites are higher than neat PLA and GF/PP, implying that smaller equivalent mass for nanocellulose-reinforced epoxy composites is required. In addition to the production of NFC from kraft pulp (0.76 kg CO₂ eq and 28 MJ) and the biosynthesis of BC (4.8 kg CO₂ eq and 131 MJ), the composite manufacturing process, whereby numerous environmental unfriendly consumables are required for VARI, also contributes to the poor environmental performance of nanocellulose-reinforced epoxy composites.

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5 REFERENCES

- [1] Wuhmann K, Heuberger A, Mühlethaler K. Elektronenmikroskopische Untersuchungen an Zellulosefasern nach Behandlung mit Ultraschall. *Experientia*. 1946;2(3):105107.
- [2] Herrick FW, Casebier RL, Hamilton JK, Sandberg KR. Microfibrillated cellulose: morphology and accessibility. In: Sarko A, editor. *Proceedings of the ninth cellulose conference*, vol. 37 Syracuse, New York: Wiley; 1983. p. 797-813.
- [3] Turbak AF, Snyder FW, Sandberg KR. Microfibrillated cellulose, a new cellulose product: properties, uses, and commercial potential. *Applied Polymer Symposium*. 1983;37:815-827.
- [4] Taniguchi T, Okamura K. New films produced from microfibrillated natural fibres. *Polym Int*. 1998;47(3):291-294.
- [5] Lee KY, Buldum G, Mantalaris A, Bismarck A. More Than Meets the Eye in Bacterial Cellulose: Biosynthesis, Bioprocessing, and Applications in Advanced Fiber Composites. *Macromol Biosci*. 2014;14(1):10-32.
- [6] Wada M, Okano T, Sugiyama J. Allomorphs of native crystalline cellulose I evaluated by two equatorial d-spacings. *J Wood Sci*. 2001;47(2):124-128.
- [7] Lee K-Y, Tammelin T, Schulfter K, Kiiskinen H, Samela J, Bismarck A. High performance cellulose nanocomposites: comparing the reinforcing ability of bacterial cellulose and microfibrillated cellulose. *ACS Appl Mater Interfaces*. 2012;4(8):4078-4086.

- [8] Boldizar A, Klason C, Kubat J, Naslund P, Saha P. Prehydrolyzed cellulose as reinforcing filler for thermoplastics. *Int J Polymer Mater.* 1987;11(4):229-262.
- [9] Yano H, Sugiyama J, Nakagaito AN, Nogi M, Matsuura T, Hikita M, et al. Optically transparent composites reinforced with networks of bacterial nanofibers. *Adv Mater.* 2005;17(2):153-155.
- [10] Sehaqui H, Zhou Q, Berglund LA. Nanostructured biocomposites of high toughness—a wood cellulose nanofiber network in ductile hydroxyethylcellulose matrix. *Soft Matter.* 2011;7(16):7342.
- [11] Li Q, McGinnis S, Sydnor C, Wong A, Renneckar S. Nanocellulose Life Cycle Assessment. *ACS Sustainable Chem Eng.* 2013;1(8):919-928.
- [12] Saito T, Kimura S, Nishiyama Y, Isogai A. Cellulose nanofibers prepared by TEMPO-mediated oxidation of native cellulose. *Biomacromolecules.* 2007;8(8):2485-2491.
- [13] Hohenthal C, Ovaskainen M, Bussini D, Sadocco P, Pajula T, Lehtinen H, et al. Final Assessment of Nano Enhanced New Products. SUNPAP; 2012.
- [14] Vink ETH, Davies S, Kolstad J. The eco-profile for current Ingeo polylactide production. *Ind Biotechnol.* 2010:212-224.
- [15] Baumann H, Tillman A-M. The Hitch Hiker's guide to LCA. An orientation in life cycle assessment methodology and application. USA2004.
- [16] Evangelisti S, Lettieri P, Borello D, Clift R. Life cycle assessment of energy from waste via anaerobic digestion: a UK case study. *Waste Manage.* 2014;34(1):226-237.
- [17] Ashby MF. *Materials Selection in Mechanical Design.* Third Edition ed. Burlington: Elsevier Butterworth-Heinemann; 2005.
- [18] Guinee J. Handbook on life cycle assessment - Operational guide to the ISO standards. *Int J Life Cycle Ass.* 2001;6(5):255-255.
- [19] Bare JC, Hofstetter P, Pennington DW, de Haes HAU. Midpoints versus endpoints: The sacrifices and benefits. *Int J Life Cycle Ass.* 2000;5(6):319-326.